

LETTER TO THE EDITOR

The emergence of unheeded clinical features in COVID-19 patients

Abhishek Kashyap¹, Poornasha Mohabeer², Jared Robinson³, Ananya Shukla⁴, Indrajit Banerjee^{5*}

***Corresponding author:**

⁵Dr. Indrajit Banerjee, Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Sir Seewoosagur Ramgoolam Medical College, Belle Rive, Mauritius

Email: indrajit18@gmail.com [[ORCID](#)]

¹Abhishek Kashyap [[ORCID](#)]

²Poornasha Mohabeer [[ORCID](#)]

³Jared Robinson [[ORCID](#)]

⁴Ananya Shukla [[ORCID](#)]

¹⁻⁴2nd Professional medical student, Sir Seewoosagur Ramgoolam Medical College, Belle Rive, Mauritius

Information about the article:

Received: Nov 20, 2020

Accepted: Dec. 14, 2020

Published online: Dec. 31, 2020

Publisher

Quest International University (QIU), No.227, Plaza Teh Teng Seng (Level 2), Jalan Raja Permaisuri Bainun, 30250 Ipoh, Perak Darul Ridzuan, Malaysia

e-ISSN: 2636-9478

© The Author(s). 2020

Content licensing: [CC BY 4.0](#)

Dear Sir,

Coronavirus disease 2019 or COVID-19 was declared as a global pandemic by the World Health Organisation (WHO) on the 11th of Mar. 2020. The first suspected case of COVID-19 was reported on the 1st of Dec. 2019 in Wuhan City, the capital of Hubei province in Central China. [1, 2] To date 71,919,725 cases have been confirmed, 1,623,064 confirmed deaths, 220 countries with active cases. (16th Dec 2020). [3] The known contagion of Coronavirus Disease is SARS-CoV-2 virus. It belongs to the sabercovirus subgenera of beta coronavirus and is the 7th coronavirus which is pathogenic to humans. [4]

While conducting a systematic review of pathogenesis and clinical manifestation of COVID-19 infection, we came across many common findings. These included headaches, dry cough, myalgia, dyspnoea, pyrexia, fatigue, breathlessness, diarrhoea, and shaking chills. pharyngalgia, anorexia, arthrodynia, COVID tongue, ulcers in the mouth, dizziness, abdominal pain, nausea, and vomiting. [5] Nevertheless, a few abnormal neurological findings were also reported, although no validated studies were conducted on these symptoms. Therefore, it is crucial to comprehend the pathogenesis of SARS-CoV-2 virus in the central nervous system. Coronavirus family infections, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS) and the Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS) has been associated with several neurological complications in the past. These viruses were neurotropic and neuroinvasive, which lead to severe inflammation and demyelination in the central nervous system. [6]

Interestingly, patients with COVID-19 are also described as similar but uncommon symptoms such as Hypogeusia (loss of taste) and Hyposmia (reduced ability to smell) or Anosmia (loss of smell). [7, 8] Currently, no tests are being performed to validate these findings, and even the pathogenesis of such neurological complications is not understood yet. [9]

According to Carod et al., coronaviruses like SARS show two propagation routes – Haematogenous route or by neuronal retrograde dissemination. In the haematogenous route, the virus can infect the blood-brain barrier's endothelial cells or infect the macrophages and Dendritic cells, which allows their entry in the central nervous system. Another route could be through Neuronal dissemination - Upon nasal inoculation, the virus disseminates via the cribriform plate and olfactory bulb,

after that, it reaches the brain stem, piriformis cortex and spinal cord. [10] These two routes could be the possible propagation mechanisms of SAR-CoV-2 virus resulting in these neurological complications.

It is strongly recommended to consider carefully the symptoms of hyposmia and hypogeusia during the provisional diagnosis of COVID-19 infection. Doctors and nurses should collect a complete medical history of each patient, including the neurological symptoms, which would further help understand neurovirulence in SARS-CoV-2 infection.

Keywords

Coronavirus, COVID-19, infection, neurological, symptoms

Abbreviations

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19), Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS), Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)

Acknowledgments

Chairman Mr. RPN Singh, Prof. Namrata Chhabra, Principal In charge, and Prof. Sushil Dawka, Sir Seewoosagar Ramgoolam Medical College, Mauritius.

Authors' contribution

- a. Study planning: AK, IB
- b. Manuscript writing: AK, PM, JR, AS, IB
- c. Manuscript revision: AK, IB
- d. Final approval: AK, PM, JR, AS, IB
- e. Agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work: AK, PM, JR, AS, IB

Funding

No funding was received.

Availability of data and materials

All data are available as part of the article, and no additional source data are required.

Competing interests

We declare no competing interests.

Publisher's Note

QIU remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

The publisher shall not be legally responsible for any types of loss, actions, claims, proceedings, demand or costs or damages whatsoever or howsoever caused arising directly or indirectly in connection with or arising out of the use of this material.

References

1. Anastassopoulou C, Russo L, Tsakris A, Siettos C. Data-based analysis, modelling and forecasting of the COVID-19 outbreak. *PLoS One*. 2020;15(3):e0230405. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0230405>
2. Banerjee I, Robinson J, Kashyap A, Mohabeer P, Shukla A, Leclézio A. The changing pattern of COVID-19 in Nepal: A Global concern- A Narrative Review. *Nepal J Epidemiol*. 2020 Jun 30;10(2):845-855. <https://doi.org/10.3126/nje.v10i2.29769>
3. WHO Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) Dashboard [Internet]. *Covid19.who.int*. 2020 [Accessed on Dec 13, 2020]. Available from: <https://covid19.who.int/>
4. Habibzadeh P, Stoneman EK. The Novel Coronavirus: A Bird's Eye View. *Int J Occup Environ Med*. 2020;11(2):65-71. <https://doi.org/10.15171/ijocem.2020.1921>
5. Liu J, Zheng X, Tong Q, Li W, Wang B, Sutter K et al. Overlapping and discrete aspects of the pathology and pathogenesis of the emerging human pathogenic coronaviruses SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, and 2019-nCoV. *J Med Virol*. 2020;92(5):491-4. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.25709>
6. Asadi-Pooya AA, Simani L. Central nervous system manifestations of COVID-19: A systematic review. *J Neurol Sci*. 2020;413:116832. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jns.2020.116832>
7. Ahmad I, Rathore FA. Neurological manifestations and complications of COVID-19: A literature review [published online ahead of print, 2020 May 6]. *J Clin Neurosci*. 2020;S0967-5868(20)31078-X. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocn.2020.05.017>
8. Banerjee I, Mohabeer P, Shukla A, Kashyap A, Robinson J. COVID-19: Recent advances in epidemiology, virology, etiopathogenesis, clinical trials and vaccine development. *J Biomed Sci*. 2020; 7(1):18-27. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jbs.v7i1.29849>
9. Lüers JC, Klußmann JP, Guntinas-Lichius O. Die COVID-19-Pandemie und das HNO-Fachgebiet: Worauf kommt es aktuell an? [The COVID-19 pandemic and otolaryngology: What it comes down to?]. *Laryngorhinootologie*. 2020;99(5):287-91. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-1095-2344>
10. Carod-Artal FJ. Neurological complications of coronavirus and COVID-19. *Complicaciones neurológicas por coronavirus y COVID-19. Rev Neurol*. 2020;70(9):311-22. <https://doi.org/10.33588/rn.7009.2020179>